

Iron (III) Chelates Of Some Substituted 8-Hydroxy Quinoline 7-Sulfonic Acids. Part I : Iron (III) 5-Chloro 8-Hydroxy Quinoline 7-Sulfonate

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Iron (III) forms in the aqueous medium a green complex with 5-chloro 8-hydroxy quinoline 7-sulfonic acid with the maximum absorbance at 600 m μ , stable in the pH range 2.5—4.5. The composition of the complex as established by three different methods spectrophotometrically is Fe(III)R (where R stands for 5-chloro 8-hydroxy quinoline 7-sulfonic acid). The stability constant calculated by the methods of Banerji and Dey and the Mole-ratio method was found to be $\log K = 3.5 \pm 0.05$ at 25° and the free energy of formation was found to be -4.91 Kcal/mole at 25°.

The introduction of 8-hydroxy quinoline for use as a reagent for the analysis of metal ions by Berg and Hahm¹ in 1926 has opened a new field in analytical chemistry. A better understanding of the specific activity of the coordinating groups in 8-hydroxy quinoline and its analogues will provide a great help in carrying out systematic work towards the improvement and greater applicability of these reagents. By condensation and substitution, certain groups can be introduced into the molecule of this organic compound so as to modify their complex forming properties.

Albert and Magrath² carried out a sensitivity test with 8-hydroxy quinoline 5-sulfonic acid and certain metal ions. It was found that many metal ions did not form a precipitate with this reagent although colour changes were observed in many cases. Banerji and Srivastava³ studied the colour reactions of 5-chloro 8-hydroxy quinoline 7-sulfonic acid with different metals and found that iron (III) develops a green colour in acidic medium. In these investigations we have prepared 5-chloro 8-hydroxy quinoline 7-sulfonic acid by the methods used by Banerji and Srivastava³ and Tio-Hsu Chang⁴. The complex formation is instantaneous and is very sensitive. As no details are available regarding the nature and the composition of the complex formed, an investigation has been made to study the complex spectrophotometrically using Job's method of continuous variation⁵, Mole-ratio method⁶, and Slope-ratio method⁷.

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EXPERIMENTAL

A standard solution of iron was prepared from a sample of Ferric chloride (B. D. H.) and the iron content was estimated. 5-chloro 8-hydroxy quinoline 7-sulfonic acid solution was prepared in double distilled water. Absorbance measurements were made by Hilger-Uvispec Spectrophotometer (Model H 700-380) using one cm effective light path. The cell compartment was fitted with a jacket which is connected to a thermostat to maintain a constant temperature of 25°. Measurements of pH were made with a Beckman pH Meter (Model H2). All the measurements were made at 25° and the chelate formed was studied under the optimum conditions.

RESULTS

Nature of the complex formed. To find out the nature of the complex formed, Voshburg and Cooper method⁸ was adopted. Mixtures containing various proportions of ferric chloride and the reagent (1 : 1, 1 : 2, 1 : 3, 1 : 4) were prepared and the absorbance at various wavelengths were taken in the visible range of spectra. The results have been graphically represented in fig. 1. It will be evident therefrom that the λ_{\max} of each mixture is found to be in the spectral region of 600m μ . It is clear

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of the mixtures of ferric chloride and 5-chloro 8-hydroxy quinoline, 7-sulfonic acid. Curve 1, reagent 1×10^{-3} M; Curve 2, $c = 1 \times 10^{-3}$ M, $p = 1$; Curve 3, $c = 5 \times 10^{-4}$ M, $p = 2$; Curve 4, $c = 3.3 \times 10^{-4}$ M, $p = 3$; Curve 5, $c = 2.5 \times 10^{-4}$ M, $p = 4$.

therefore that only one complex is formed under the conditions of study. The absorbance of the ligand does not show any maxima in the visible region of the spectrum as may also be seen in fig. 1.

Effect of pH on the chelate: Solutions containing the same concentration of the reagent and ferric chloride were prepared at different pH and the absorbance at various wavelengths were taken. The complex showed λ_{\max} at 600m μ in the pH range

1.5 to 5, and it gave a constant optical density at $600m\mu$ in the pH range 2.5 to 4.5 (fig. 2)

Fig. 2. Effect of pH on the chelate, Curve 1, Effect of pH on absorption maxima. Curve 2, Effect of pH on optical density at $600m\mu$.

Composition of the complex: As has been said before, the composition of the complex was studied by three different methods.

(1) *Job's method:* Job's method of continuous variation⁵ has been adopted for determining the composition of the coloured complex formed. The absorbance of the mixture, metal ion, and the chelating agent were measured at two different wavelengths of $600m\mu$ and $585m\mu$, using both equimolar and non-equimolar solutions, adjusting the pH to 4. Some of the representative results have been shown in figs. 3 and 4.

Fig. 3. Determination of composition by Job's method using equimolar solutions. Curve 1, $c=2 \times 10^{-3}M$, $p=1$; Curve 2, $c=1.42 \times 10^{-3}M$, $p=1$; Curve 3, $c=1.11 \times 10^{-3}M$, $p=1$; Curve 4, $c=1 \times 10^{-3}M$, $p=1$.

Fig. 4. Job's method using non-equimolar solutions. Curve 1, $c=4 \times 10^{-3}M$, $p=2$; Curve 2, $c=2.84 \times 10^{-3}M$, $p=2$; Curve 3, $c=2.22 \times 10^{-3}M$, $p=2$; Curve 4, $c=1.82 \times 10^{-3}M$, $p=2$.

(2) *Mole-ratio method*: In the determination of the composition by Mole-ratio method⁶ a series of solutions were prepared from $2 \times 10^{-3} M$ of the eagentand equimolar solutions of the metal ion in such a way that the mole-ratio of the reagent to metal was from 1 : 0.2 to 1 : 5. The results obtained have been plotted in fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Mole-ratio method at $600m\mu$.
Final concentration of reagent, Curve A $1.12 \times 10^{-3} M$; Curve B $1 \times 10^{-3} M$.

As will be seen from the same, a break occurs at the ratio reagent : metal 1 : 1, indicating the composition of the complex is 1 : 1.

(3) *Slope-ratio method*: In the determination by Slope-ratio method⁷ the concentration of the variable component was varied from 1×10^{-5} to $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ in presence of an excess concentration ($2 \times 10^{-3} M$) of the constant component. The pH of the solutions were adjusted to 4. Fig. 6 shows the absorbance measurements at

Fig. 6. Slope-ratio method.
10 ml excess component ($2 \times 10^{-3} M$) + V^1 ml ($1 \times 10^{-3} M$)
variable component + $(10 - v)$ ml water.
Curve 1-1 Metal varying, Curve 2-2 Reagent varying.
Solid lines refer to $600m\mu$. Broken lines refer to $585m\mu$.

two different wavelengths of 585 and 600m μ , plotted against the concentration of the variable component. The slope of the two straight lines provide iron : reagent as 1: 1.

For the purpose of the determination of the stability constant of the complex, calculations have been made by the method used by Banerji and Dey⁹ and by the Mole ratio method⁶. The value of log K in this system of iron-5 chloro 8-hydroxy quinoline 7-sulfonate, works out to be 3.5 ± 0.05 at 25°. The free energy of formation of the chelate investigated here is -4.91 Kcal/mole at 25°.

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